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In-air Production of 3D Co-culture Tumor Spheroid Hydrogels for Expedited Drug Screening

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Abstract

Three-dimensional (3D) *in vitro* tumor spheroids are becoming popular as pre-clinical platforms for testing the performance of existing drugs or for discovery of innovative anticancer therapeutics. This focus is correlated with *in vitro* 3D tumor models ability to mimic the multicellular compact structure and spatial architecture of human solid tumors. However, these microphysiological systems generally lack the pre-existence of tumor-ECM, a critical aspect that can affect the overall therapeutic performance and the decision of advancing candidate drugs to later stages of the pipeline. Aiming to face this drawback and mimic tumors-ECM, herein we rapidly fabricated in-air hyaluronan-methacrylate (HA-MA) and gelatin-methacrylate (GelMA) photocrosslinkable 3D spheroid microgels by using superhydrophobic surfaces. These platforms were used for establishing heterotypic 3D coculture models of prostate cancer cells (PC-3) and human osteoblasts (hOB) to mimic prostate cancer-to-bone metastasis cellular heterogeneity and the tumor-ECM microenvironment. 3D microgel microtumors morphology, size and cell number were easily controlled via digital droplet generation on polystyrene superhydrophobic surfaces and under solvent-free conditions when compared to microfluidics or electrospray. Co-culture 3D microgels formed by 2.5%HA-MA-5%GelMA and 5%HA-MA-5%GelMA ratios showed the highest calcium deposition after 14 days of culture, evidencing osteoblasts viability and the establishment of functional mineralization in the 3D hydrogel matrix. Cisplatin cytotoxicity evaluation showed that 3D microgels are more resistant to platin chemotherapeutics than single or co-culture 3D multicellular spheroid counterparts. Overall, our findings indicate that solvent-free, in-air produced 3D microgel microenvironments are cost-effective and robust tumor mimicking platforms for *in vitro* high-throughput screening of therapeutics targeted to prostate-to-bone metastasis microenvironments.

Keywords: Superhydrophobic surface, 3D *in vitro* tumor models, Spherical Microgels, Drug Screening

1. Introduction

Prostate cancer, is the second most commonly diagnosed cancer in men worldwide [1] and despite significant medical advances, prostate cancer is still one of the leading causes of cancer-related death in men [2-4]. Prostate cancer, represents a complex disease normally highly susceptible to androgen regulation and encompassing the establishment of immune-suppressive microenvironments [5]. Ultimately this tumor supportive microenvironment if untreated can, in advanced stages of the disease, lead to cancer cell invasion, migration and metastasis [5,6].

Prostate cancer metastasis to bone tissues occurs normally due to the unique growth-factor rich microenvironment of the bone-marrow [7]. Metastasis from prostate cancer cells to the bone is a complex process involving several stages: i) malignant cells evasion from the primary site towards the blood or lymph nodes, ii) migration and fixation of tumor cells in bone tissues and iii) development of a new tumor at in the bone tissue [8-10]. Understanding the role of native bone cells (e.g., osteoblasts, osteocytes, osteoclasts, hematopoietic cells, mesenchymal cells, and immune cells) and how they interact with prostate cancer cells, is an important aspect for the development of more effective therapeutics [9]. Throughout the whole process from the primary tumor to its metastatic niche, it is widely accepted that non-malignant cells actively influence the fate of cancer cells [8]. Factors secreted by prostate cancer cells modulate osteoblasts bioactivity which ultimately leads to disease progression Prostate cancer metastasis can cause osteoblasts to promote excessive bone formation, to acquire a osteolytic behavior (bone lysis), or trigger a mixed response [11,12]. Several studies have reported that about 90% of patients with advanced prostate cancer will develop bone metastasis [8-10]. Presentation of secondary tumors is associated with high levels of morbidity and mortality, in part due to the lack of effective therapies in the clinic. This scenario evidences the urgent need to discover new therapeutic approaches that can realistically impact patient survival rates.

The pre-clinical discovery of new anti-cancer therapeutics using both 2D *in vitro* cell cultures and animal models, involves high costs and ethics issues associated with the use of rodents and has demonstrated a very low correlation with data obtained in clinical trials [12,14]. Adding to this, in the pharmaceuticals discovery process it is clear that 2D *in vitro* cultures do not represent the 3D spatial environment of a human tumor, nor its extracellular matrix (ECM) or stromal cellular components [12,15]. To overcome these issues 3D *in vitro* tumor models have been researched in the last two decades as potential alternative testing platforms for new anti-cancer drugs screening [16,17]. Currently the most used scaffold-free 3D tumor models are cell-spheroids which are

cellular aggregates formed by cancer cells. There are various technologies for 3D spheroids assembly such as those based on ultra-low adhesion cell culture plates (Corning® Costar® Ultra-Low attachment multi-well plates[18], or micromolding techniques (MicroTissues® 3D Petri Dish® micro-mold spheroids[19]). Given their tumor-like features, *in vitro* multicellular spheroids have been particularly useful for studying the efficacy of innovative chemotherapeutic agents for prostate cancer [20],[21].

However, these scaffold-free models do not include tumor ECM components at their initial stage of assembly. The development of 3D *in vitro* tumor models should take into consideration the inclusion of tumor ECM components, as these trigger key physicochemical responses [22]. Biomaterials provide an excellent platform to include ECM-like cues, but the composition and organization still need to be optimized [12]. In particular, there is a need to develop ECM mimicking biomaterials with suitable mechanical rigidity, 3D architecture, structural organization and cell adhesion, so as to recapitulate in an increasingly reliable form the tumor microenvironment of human tumors [23,24]. Natural-origin biomaterials (e.g., chitosan, alginate, collagen, hyaluronic acid), have been exploited for the manufacture of 3D tumor scaffolds, such as hydrogel matrixes, as they replicate cancer cells-ECM interactions present in the native tumor microenvironment [24]. However, in hydrogel matrixes the cell number comprising self-forming 3D agglomerates and their shape is highly difficult to control within the gel volume leading to variable drug responses. Cells bioencapsulation in spherically shaped microgels may provide therefore a valuable alternative to address these issues if controllable and cost-effective sphere generating technologies such as hydrophobic surfaces or microfluidic chips are employed.

Superhydrophobic surfaces, have been used in the field of biomedicine, regenerative medicine and tissue engineering as platforms for biomaterials processing and also for high throughput screening (HTS) and 3D cell niches manufacturing, [25-31]. By using hydrophobized surfaces virtually 100% cell encapsulation is possible and control over spheroids size can be easily attained by adjusting the number of encapsulated cells and the volume of dispensed droplets [26,32,33].

In this work we produced a new 3D model of metastatic prostate cancer that mimics prostate cancer bone metastasis cellular heterogeneity and ECM microenvironment. The 3D models are comprised of methacrylated hyaluronic acid and gelatin-methacryloyl (HA-MA and GelMA). Interest in these two biopolymers is related to the fact that GelMA is chemically similar to native tissues ECM [34] and hyaluronic acid is an abundant structural component in the extracellular matrix of prostate cancer [6,35]. These two methacrylated macromers can be crosslinked by

photopolymerization and form a stable network through covalent crosslinking. Cells were encapsulated using superhydrophobic surfaces for the formation of spherical microgels that were then subjected to photocrosslinking through U.V. light incidence. The produced spheroidal microtumors have reproducible spherical morphology, it is possible to control the number of encapsulated cells and the size is adjustable with the volume of the drop dispensed on the superhydrophobic surface. We performed several monoculture assays with different biopolymer concentrations and cell densities, and the two best formulations were used for development of prostate cancer- human osteoblast (PC-3/hOB) 3D multicellular heterotypic drug testing platforms.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Hyaluronic acid sodium salt polymer (MW: 80 - 100 kDa) was obtained from Carbosynth Ltd (Berkshire, United Kingdom). Gelatin Type A from porcine skin, Irgacure 2959, and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF 99.8 %) were acquired from Merk-Sigma (Sintra, Portugal). The regenerated cellulose Spectra/Por® dialysis membrane with 6-8 kDa MWCO was purchased from Spectrum Labs (Spectrum, CA, US). Triethylamine (TEA, 99 %), Glycidyl methacrylate (97 %) were obtained from ACROS organics. L-Ascorbic Acid 2-Phosphate was obtained from VWR (VWR International, Carnaxide, Portugal). Water and Ice Repellent Satellite Coating (WX2100) was acquired from Cytonix and Cisplatin were purchased from Biogen. All of the following cell culture media and supplements namely GIBCO® Dulbecco's Phosphate buffered saline (DPBS), Trypan Blue, Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS; E.U. approved, South America origin), Roswell Park Memorial Institute RPMI-1640 Medium, Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM F-12), TrypLE™ Express, GIBCO® Antibiotic/antimycotic solution (ATB) containing 10,000 units/mL of penicillin, 10,000 pg/mL of streptomycin, and 25 pg/mL of Gibco Amphotericin B were purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific (Alfagene, Portugal). Ultra-Low-Adhesion (ULA) round-bottom 96-wells plates were purchased from Corning (Corning, NY, US). Calcein-AM, Propidium Iodide (PI) and P-Glycerol phosphate were all purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc (Alfagene, Carcavelos, Portugal). Alizarin Red S was obtained from Laborspirit (Loures, Portugal). CellTiter-Glo® was obtained from Promega (Madison, WI, USA). The PC-3 cell line derived from a bone metastasis of a grade IV prostate adenocarcinoma was obtained from ATCC (PC-3 (ATCC® CRL-1435™)), and primary fetal human osteoblasts were acquired from Cell Applications Inc. (San Diego, CA, US).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Synthesis of methacrylated hyaluronic acid

Methacrylated hyaluronic acid (HA-MA) was synthesized by reacting hyaluronic acid with glycidyl methacrylate under alkaline conditions based on the methodology described before [36]. In brief, hyaluronic acid (HA) (2.0 g) was dissolved in distilled water (100 mL) in a 500 mL round bottom flask, under magnetic stirring, at room temperature (RT), to yield a 2 % w/v aqueous solution. Afterwards, glycidyl methacrylate (35.5 mL) and TEA (25.3 mL) were drop-wised added to 39.2 mL of DMF, in a Schott Flask under magnetic stirring, in a chemical fume hood.

Afterwards, the organic DMF phase was added to HA aqueous phase *via* drop-wise addition, and the reaction proceeded for 72 h, at RT protected from light. After this period the modified polymer solution was carefully transferred to a regenerated cellulose dialysis membrane (MWCO 6-8 kDa), and dialyzed against DI water for 5 days, at RT. The purified solution was then frozen at -80 °C and freeze-dried for 5 days, in the dark. The resulting methacrylated hyaluronic acid (HA-MA) polymer was recovered as a white cotton foam.

2.2.2. Synthesis of Methacrylated Gelatin

Porcine gelatin type A was chemically modified with methacryloyl functional moieties as previously described by Loessner and co-workers, with slight modifications [37]. Initially, a 10 % (w/v) gelatin solution was prepared by dissolving gelatin in PBS (pH = 7.4), under vigorous magnetic stirring, at 50 °C, overnight, to achieve complete dissolution. Afterwards, 0.6 g of methacrylic anhydride per 1 g of dissolved gelatin (very viscous liquid) was added slowly to the mixture for a high degree of methacryloyl functionalization and the reaction was left to proceed for 5 h, at RT, under stirring. Afterwards, the solution was transferred into 50 mL tubes and centrifuged at 3500 g for 3 min, at RT, to remove unreacted methacrylic anhydride. The GelMA containing supernatant was then decanted and the unreacted methacrylic anhydride discarded. The supernatant was then diluted with 10 mL of deionized water and transferred to a regenerated cellulose dialysis membrane (MWCO 6-8 kDa). GelMA was dialyzed at 50 °C against deionized water during 5 to 7 days protected from light. The purified methacrylated polymer was then freeze dried as above mentioned.

2.2.3. Functionalized Biopolymers Spectroscopic Characterization

The inclusion of the acrylate-based photoreactive moieties in the different biopolymers was initially characterized by proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectroscopy. All spectra were acquired on a Bruker Advance III 300 MHz spectrometer. For NMR analysis all samples were dissolved in deuterated water (D₂O) and transferred to 300 MHz NMR glass tubes (Wilmad, Cortenet, France). Samples were acquired with 256 scans, 8 dummy scans and with 18 secs of relaxation delay. The acquired spectra were processed by using the MestReNova v6.0.2 software. ¹H NMR data was used to determine HA degree of methacrylation as described in the literature [38,39].

In addition, the chemically modified ECM-mimetic biopolymers were characterized by attenuated

total reflectance Fourier Transformed Infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR). For analysis, powdered samples were placed in a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer. A total of 256 scans, with a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ were acquired in the spectral window spanning from 4000 to 350 cm⁻¹. The obtained data was processed in OPUS software and plotted in Origin software (v9.1, trial version).

2.2.4. Fluoraldehyde assay for GelMA characterization

The fluoraldehyde assay was used to determine the degree of acrylate functionalization (DoF) as previously described in the literature, with minor modifications [37]. For this purpose, initially, a freshly prepared gelatin stock solution (0.5 mg/mL, in PBS pH =7.4) was used for computing a standard curve (0.02, 0.1, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 mg/mL). Before the experiments, fluoraldehyde reagent was warmed to RT. For samples analysis, 300 pL of GelMA (10% w/v) were mixed with 600 pL of the fluoraldehyde reagent. Control samples were prepared by mixing 300 pL of PBS with 600 pL of the fluoraldehyde reagent under vortex for 1 min. After 5 min of incubation 250 pL of each solution were placed in a 96-well black-clear bottom plate, and the fluorescence intensity ($X_{ex}=360$ nm, $X_{em}=450$ nm) was measured by using a plate reader (Synergy HTX, BioTek Instruments, US). The average fluorescence intensity and the fluorescence intensity of PBS control was subtracted from the sample to determine net fluorescence. The DoF was then calculated as $DoF = ((0.5 - G)/0.5) \times 100 \%$, where G is gelatin concentration in mg/mL.

2.2.5. Production of Superhydrophobic Polystyrene Surfaces (PS)

The production of polystyrene (PS) superhydrophobic surfaces was performed by using a simple, economical and fast procedure. In brief, circular polystyrene 90 mm petri dish plates were spray coated with U.V. resistant FluoroThane-MW reagent (WX 2100™) that provides a contact angle of about 150°, as described by the manufacturer (Cytonix, MD, US). The entire petri dish surface was spray coated and left to dry overnight in a chemical safety fume hood, at room temperature. In the following day, the surface was washed with 99 % ethanol and oven dried at 37 °C for 5 days.

2.2.6. In-air production of spheroidal 3D microgels

Spheroidal microgels were produced by using a mechanical electronic repeater pipette (Eppendorf® M4, Eppendorf, VWR) to dispense biopolymer aqueous solutions (1.25 % to 5 % w/v) onto polystyrene superhydrophobic surfaces. Spheroidal hydrogel droplets of different sizes were formed by dispensing various volumes (1 pL to 5 pL, Figure 5). The droplets were then photocrosslinked by using Irgacure 2959 (1 % w/v) as a photoinitiator and a U.V. curing system

(Omniculture® S2000, Excelitas Technologies, US) that was used to irradiate hydrogels for 2 min, at an intensity of 0.86 mW/cm² (measured via a U.V.-vis radiometer R2000 - 250-1000 nm, Omniculture®). Through this approach, different ECM- mimetic spheroidal hydrogels formed by HA-MA and HA-MA/GelMA blends were obtained.

2.2.7. Spheroidal microgels morphological characterization

Spheroidal microgels size and morphological characterization was performed by optical contrast microscopy and optical imaging. For size evaluation different microgel droplets were imaged in a stereomicroscope (Zeiss Stemi 508, Carl Zeiss, Germany), equipped with a 3MPix color camera, and in an upright optical contrast microscope (Zeiss Primostar, Carl Zeiss, Germany) equipped with a A-Plan 5x/0.12 Ph0 M27 objective. Macrographs of spheroidal hydrogel particles were also acquired by using a Canon EOS 1200d DLSR camera equipped with a macro lens.

2.2.8. 2D *In vitro* Cell culture

In general, cells were cultured under aseptic conditions in temperature-controlled cell culture incubators at 37 °C and with a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Routinely, cells were grown in T-75 and T-175 cm² cell culture flasks, with cell culture media changes every other day. The human osteoblast cell line (hOB) was cultured in DMEM-F12 medium supplemented with 10 % (v/v) FBS, 1 % (v/v) ATB and ascorbic acid (50 µg/mL, in PBS pH=7.4). The human prostate cancer cell line (PC-3) was maintained in RPMI 1640 medium (Glucose 2.5 g/L), supplemented with 10 % (v/v) FBS and 1 % (v/v) ATB. Upon attaining a confluency of approximately 80-85 % all cells were detached from culture flasks by using TrypLE™ Express as detaching reagent.

2.2.9. Formulation of cell laden spheroidal 3D *in vitro* tumor models

Formulation of monotypic and heterotypic cell laden 3D spheroidal microgels was performed by using superhydrophobic surfaces and U.V. mediated photocrosslinking. Initially, cells were detached as above mentioned and resuspended in equal volumes of HAMA and GelMA and mixed to obtain a homogeneous cell dispersion. After crosslinking for 2 min under U.V. light (λ= 365 nm, 0.86 mW/cm²), 3D microgels were washed in DPBS and transferred to Ultra-Low-Adhesion (ULA) round-bottom 96-wells plates. 3D microgels were cultured in 200 µL of culture medium, at 37 °C and in a 5 % CO₂ atmosphere.

For the establishment of 3D co-culture microgels, PC-3 bone metastasis cells as well as hOB were trypsinized and mixed at a PC-3:hOB 1:1 ratio. The cells were then dispersed in the tumor-ECM

mimetic HA-MA/GelMA matrix and droplet spotted in the superhydrophobic surfaces for U.V. photocrosslinking as before mentioned. In addition, standard 3D co-culture spheroids (controls) were directly established in ULA round-bottom plates by dispersing PC-3/hOB cell mixtures in these 96 well plates. During all co-culture experiments the culture medium was 50% RPMI 1640 and 50% DMEM F12 with 50 pL/mg ascorbic acid and 2.16 mg/mL of P-Glycerol phosphate. These last two compounds were added at day 3 and 7 of culture to mimic the microenvironment found in PC-3 bone metastasis. 3D *in vitro* tumor models (spheroids and microgels) morphology and shape were analyzed overtime via optical contrast microscopy by using an inverted microscope (Primovert, Carl Zeiss, Germany). Images were acquired at specific timepoints (3, 7 and 14 days).

2.2.10. Cell Viability assays

The cell viability of 3D spheroidal micro-tumors in mono and co-culture were analyzed at 3, 7 and 14 days by using: (i) AlamarBlue® Cell Viability Assay and (ii) Live / Dead Assay. AlamarBlue® was used to evaluate metabolical activity of monocultured and co-cultured 3D tumor models. All the assays were performed according to the manufacturer's guidelines. In AlamarBlue® Resazurin reduction to pink colored resorufin was determined by fluorescence measurements (k_{ex} : 540 nm, k_{em} : 600 nm). All measurements were performed in a Synergy HTX microplate reader by using a 96-well black-clear flat bottom plate (Costar, VWR). To assess cell viability, the microtumors were labeled with Calcein-AM (3 pg/mL) and Propidium Iodide (PI) (6 pg/mL) for 45 min at 37 °C. Following incubation, the 3D tumor models were washed 3 times with DPBS and immediately analyzed by using fluorescence microscopy. Fluorescence micrographs were acquired in an upright Widefield fluorescence microscope (Zeiss Imager M2, Carl Zeiss, Germany), equipped with an EC Plan-Neofluar 5x/0.16 objective and a 3MPix monochromatic camera. All micrographs were acquired and processed in Zeiss Zen SP2 Software (Carl Zeiss, Germany).

2.2.11. 3D *in vitro* tumor calcium deposit evaluation

To detect the calcium deposition, cultured 3D tumor spheroidal microgels were stained with Alizarin Red S dye. For this purpose, 3D tumors were initially fixed in 4% formaldehyde overnight, before incubation with 150 pL of Alizarin Red S (40 mM, pH=4.2), for 2 h in the dark, at RT. After incubation, the staining solution was aspirated and 3D microgels were rinsed three times with

deionized water. All images were acquired at specific timepoints (7 and 14 days) by using a Stemi 508 Stereo Microscope (Carl Zeiss, Germany).

2.2.12. Cell-specific tracking in 3D microgels

Cell tracking assays were performed to evaluate the cellular organization within the produced HA-MA / GelMA 3D microgels. For this purpose, the distinct cellular populations of PC-3 and hOB were differentially stained with long-term cell tracking lipophilic dyes DiO and DiD (Thermo Fisher scientific, Alfacene, Portugal), as per the manufacturer instructions. Briefly, 5 pL of staining agent were added to 1 mL of serum free culture medium containing 1×10^6 cells. The solutions containing both cells and staining agents were then incubated for 30 min at 37 °C, after which 3 sequential washings/centrifugation steps using serum containing medium, were performed. To prevent damage, between washing-centrifugation cycles, cells were allowed to equilibrate for 10 min, at 37 °C, after each wash.

PC-3 were stained with DiO (blue), and hOB with DiD (red). These cell tracking dyes are transferrable to subsequent cellular generations as recommended by the manufacturer. Widefield fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Imager M2, Carl Zeiss, Germany) was used for the analysis of 3D microgels, containing PC-3 (DiO) and hOB (DiD) stained populations, at day 7 and 14. This strategy is highly valuable since it allows a qualitative assessment of both localization and aggregation patterns of the different cell populations inside the 3D models.

2.2.13. Chemotherapeutic drug cytotoxicity screening in 3D *in vitro* tumor models

3D models of *in vitro* tumors in co-cultures were used as testing platforms for the evaluation of cisplatin cytotoxicity. On day 7 of culture 3D *in vitro* models were incubated with cisplatin at different concentrations (100 pM, 150 pM, and 250 pM) [40], for 48 h. Cell viability was assessed in 3D cell aggregates *in vitro* by quantifying cellular ATP through a luminescence-based assay specific for 3D cell culture (3D Cell Titer Glo Luminescent viability assay, Promega, Madison, WI, USA). CellTiter-Glo® assays were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions. After cisplatin incubation, the medium was removed and 3D tumor models were incubated with a mixture of RPMI 1640 complete medium and CellTiter-Glo® reagent at a ratio of 1:1. The mixture was then stirred for 5 min and incubated for 25 min, at RT. Luminescence was measured on 96-well opaque flat bottom white plates by using a Synergy HTX microplate reader programmed with an integration time of 1 sec.

2.2.14. Statistical Analysis

Data and statistical was performed by using GraphPad Prism 6 Software (Prism 6™, trial version). One-way analysis of variance (One-ANOVA) with Holm-Sidak post-hoc test was generally used. A value of $p < 0.05$ was deemed statistically significant.

3. Results and Discussion

The body of knowledge regarding the involvement of the tumor microenvironment as a barrier or promoter of primary tumors progression is constantly being expanded [41]. Being a complex multifactorial hotspot, the tumor microenvironment is comprised by both cellular and extracellular matrix (ECM) components that are modulated and modulate disease progression in a highly dynamic process. Moreover, when metastasis to distant organs occurs, the supporting microenvironment of secondary sites becomes equally important, especially for the screening of innovative anti-tumoral and anti-metastatic therapeutics. The development of rationally bioengineered *in vitro* 3D cancer models that are able to mimic the major hallmarks of prostate-to-bone metastasis is currently highly desired by pharmaceutical companies and physicians.

In this context, hyaluronan and collagen have been reported as two major components of the tumor-ECM present in the prostate-to-bone metastatic niche [42]. Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a non-thrombogenic and non-immunogenic anionic biopolymer, that consists of D-N- acetylglucosamine and D-glucuronic acid repeating units, covalently linked through alternating P-1,4 and P-1,3 glycosidic bonds [43,44]. This polysaccharide is well-recognized as a major ECM component in a variety of tissues, is highly expressed in bone ECM, and is highly associated with prostate cancer progression [6,35,45,46]. It is produced by hyaluronan synthases and secreted into the extracellular space as a constituent of the extracellular matrix [46, 50-51]. Interestingly, hyaluronan receptor, i.e., cluster of differentiation 44 (CD44) is highly expressed by motile prostate cancer epithelial cells and associated stromal cells. Moreover, HA is highly concentrated within the tumor-associated stromal ECM, making it an integral component of the metastatic bone microenvironment [50-52].

Gelatin is a biocompatible material which has been widely used for mimicking collagen in *in vitro* disease models engineering, since it also promotes cell adhesion and proliferation, also it can be used alone or in combination with other biomaterials [53]. Gelatin is obtained by partially hydrolyzing collagen, which comprises approximately 95 % of the organic matrix of bone [9], [47]. It contains integrin binding sequences (e.g., Arg-Gly-Asp - RGD) and protease sensitive sites for matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), being chemically similar to native tissues ECM [53]. This biomaterial degrades due to its matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) sensitive protein sequences, which are essential to allow for the deposition of newly formed ECM.

The natural availability of these biomaterials and their biological relevancy renders them key components to be included in bioengineered 3D cancer models that aim to recapitulate *in vitro*

prostate-to-bone secondary tumors. Nevertheless, to use HA or gelatin for generating 3D *in vitro* tumor models, a chemical modification is generally required for crosslinking it into a 3D hydrogel scaffold that can be employed for bioencapsulation of cancer cells. Therefore, herein we initially modified gelatin and HA macromers with methacryloyl moieties to allow a rapid and reproducible generation of prostate cancer cells laden spheroidal 3D microgels via droplet spotting and U.V. mediated photocrosslinking in a superhydrophobic surface.

3.1. Spectroscopic characterization of methacrylated biopolymers

Hyaluronic acid consists of two saccharide rings as a repeating unit that endows it with biodegradable and biocompatible properties. As mentioned before, the polymer was chemically methacrylated (MA) to facilitate crosslinking upon exposure to U.V. light [44]. In particular, HA was conjugated with a methacrylate moiety through a rapid reaction with glycidyl methacrylate, as reported in the literature [36], to obtain methacrylated hyaluronic acid (HA-MA). The ^1H NMR spectra shown in Figure 1 allowed the confirmation of a successful substitution of HA functional hydroxyl groups due to the presence of two new peaks with a chemical shift at $\delta=5.8$ ppm and $\delta=6.2$ ppm represent the methacrylate vinyl groups (Figure 1 A) [41]. These peaks were not present in the unmodified HA. The peaks in box 2 and 3 located at approximately $\delta=1.8$ ppm and $\delta=2.1$ ppm respectively, were assigned to the methyl groups (Figure 1 A).

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B Figure 1. ¹H NMR spectra of: A) methacrylated HA (HA-MA) and B) methacrylated Gelatin (GelMA), obtained in D₂O in a 300 MHz spectrometer. Blue and green lines represent HA-MA and GelMA backbones, respectively.

In addition, HA methacrylation was also evaluated by using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (Supplementary Figure S1). The obtained spectra demonstrated a new peak at ~1730 cm⁻¹,

which can be assigned to the C=O. A second new peak at 1643 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the C=C bond was also observed (Supplementary Figure S1). These findings further corroborate the successful functionalization of HA polymeric backbone with methacrylate moieties. In addition to HA, also gelatin was chemically modified to allow the formation of tailored spheroidal hydrogels.

Although raw gelatin can form physically crosslinked hydrogels through temperature- induced gelation, a high concentration of gelatin is often needed for this process. Moreover, the resulting raw gelatin hydrogels have poor mechanical properties and disassemble under *in vitro* cell culture conditions (e.g., at 37 °C). Gelatin has abundant amino, hydroxyl, and carboxyl functional chemical groups that can be used for precision modification. To assure hydrogel stability, a number of crosslinking strategies in these groups have been adopted, including the use of chemical modification to support photocrosslinking. Methacrylic anhydride (MA) is currently the most widely used agent for such modification [37]. To allow the formation of spherical hydrogels via photocrosslinking we synthesized gelatin- methacryloyl through the reaction of MA monomers with lysine and hydroxy lysine groups present in gelatin. Following synthesis, gelatin and GelMA were characterized by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. As the results in Figure 1B demonstrate, the MA modification was confirmed by the decrease in lysine protons signal at $\delta = 3.31$ ppm observed in GelMA. In addition, the increase in the methacrylate vinyl group signal at $\delta = 5.7$ ppm and $\delta = 5.9$ ppm and the methyl group signal at $\delta = 2.2$ ppm reinforce the occurrence of the linkage between MA and gelatin.

3.2. Characterization of biopolymer degree of substitution

Following chemical modification of HA and gelatin polymeric backbone the degree of substitution was calculated. As described in the literature, HA polymeric backbone degree of substitution was calculated by the integrated intensity of the double bond protons to those of HA [36]. The synthesized HA derivative exhibited ~35% methacrylation, indicating that a significant amount of HA monomers is modified with photocrosslinkable groups. It is important to emphasize that the multiplicity of peaks observed between $\delta=3.0$ ppm and $\delta=3.8$ ppm may be attributed to the high degree of HA methacrylation as also described in other recent reports [36].

To estimate gelatin degree of functionalization the fluoraldehyde assay was performed. To this end, after measuring the fluorescence of each standard gelatin solution, a calibration curve was established which correlated fluorescence with gelatin concentration (Supplementary Figure S2). From the calibration curve obtained, and the average absorbance readout for the GelMA sample, the

respective gelatin concentration was calculated. The degree of substitution obtained for GelMA was 89.53%. This result is in accordance with those reported in recent studies that also employ PBS (pH= 7.4) as reaction buffer [50].

3.3. 3D Spheroidal microgels generation and characterization

In order to assess which conditions of micro-tumor production would allow an ideal size, to recapitulate of such physiological conditions, distinct volumes of HA-MA droplets were dispensed with a digital repeater pipette on superhydrophobic surfaces. The particle diameter of HA-MA microgel formulations (1pL, 2pL, 3pL, and 5pL) was evaluated to determine the most appropriate size to recapitulate a 3D microtumor *in vitro*. Figure 2 demonstrates that particle size steadily increased with the increase of the deposited droplet volume. The HAMA spheroidal gels showed a slightly reduced size in comparison to the theoretical values for perfect spheres. We hypothesize that this is related to the viscosity of the HA-MA solution and to the evaporation during the 2 min U.V. photocrosslinking.

The volume of 1 pL was selected due to its submillimeter size (~821 pm) that would allow the comparison of microgel 3D *in vitro* models with standard cell-rich spheroids formed in the literature. It is important to mention that this is an innovative approach which easily allows a rapid and controllable production of spherical microgel constructs compatible with high throughput screening and downstream analysis (e.g. live/dead, cell viability assays).

Particles spherical shape was also analyzed by stereomicroscopy and standard optical contrast microscopy. The obtained results demonstrate that all 3D microgel formulations have a well-defined spherical shape (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Characterization of 3D HA microgels. A) Schematics of 3D microgels formulation in superhydrophobic surfaces and size control via droplet dispensing. B) Variation of particle diameters with increasing droplet. Measurement of the diameter of the various particle sizes was performed in the ImageJ software. Data is presented as mean \pm s.d, n= 12. Blue squares denote theoretical size. C) Optical photograph size variation with deposited volume (side view). D) Particles with volumes from 1 pL to 5 pL observed by stereomicroscopy. E) Particles with volumes from 1pL to 5pL observed by optical contrast microscopy. Scale bars represent 500 pm.

3.5. HA-MA 3D monotypic tumor microgels assembly

To optimize PC-3 cells cell density in 3D microgels, particles with different HA concentrations and encapsulation of a low cell density (4000 PC-3 cells), and a high cell density (20000 PC-3 cells) were investigated. As visualized in Figure 3, microgels formed

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at the lowest HA concentration (2.5% w/v) were destroyed in culture. For this reason, only HA concentrations from 5% to 10% (w/v) were used for further studies. From the obtained optical images, it is clear that higher cell density and cellular compaction was observed for the bioencapsulation of 20000 cells in 3D microgels volume when compared to 3D models with the lowest cell encapsulation

density.

PC-3 20000 cells

PC-3 4000 cells

HA-MA 5

HA-MA 10%

Time (days)

PC-3 20000 cells

HA 5% MA 10%

Figure 3. Follow up of cancer cells bioencapsulation in 3D HA microgels along time. A) Optical micrographs of PC-3 cell laden 3D microgels formed by different HA-MA concentrations. B) Optical micrographs of HA 5% and HA 10%. 3D microgels encapsulating 20000 PC-3 cells per particle. C and D) Assessment of PC-3 cells viability in 3D HA microgels along time. Data is presented as mean \pm s.d, n= 5. E) Time course Live/Dead analysis of higher cell density particles (20000 PC-3 cells per particle). Green channel live cells - Calcein-AM, Red channel necrotic cells: PI.

The metabolic activity was verified by AlamarBlue (Figure 3 C and D) and cell death by using the Live/Dead assay (Figure 3 E). The obtained results indicate that even with an increase in cell number per particle, the metabolic activity decreases over time, particularly at 14 days. We hypothesize that such results are a consequence of HA poor cell adhesive properties since it lacks major cell adhesion domains such as RGD, YIGSR or IKVAV. This was further corroborated by the increase in dead cells observed in the Live-dead assay (Figure 3 E). Despite this decrease in viability, no necrotic core formation was observable in all 3D microgel models. Instead, generalized cell death seemed to occur, perhaps as result of cells incapacity to properly adhere to the microgel matrix. Such observations are concordant with previous reports, where cells cultured within HA scaffolds lose the ability to adhere and acquire a physiological 3D conformation [44]. Owing to these findings we included gelatin as a second ECM mimetic component of the prostate-to-bone tumor microenvironment.

3.5.1. HA-MA/GelMA 3D monotypic tumor microgels assembly

Contrarily to HA, gelatin is a well-established natural cell-supportive scaffold containing extensive collagen fragments to which cells can adhere through integrins and is known for its well reported biocompatibility and ECM-mimicking properties. As such, the use of GelMA for microgels formation was hypothesized to not only improve cell adhesion properties of 3D microgels matrix, but also to provide crucial collagen I motifs that mimic those of native bone tissue. Gelatin addition was performed in a (1:1) volume ratio to HA. Initially, HA-MA and GelMA microgels were produced via U.V.-mediated photocrosslinking, allowing the generation of 3D microgels for studying cell-cell and cell- biomaterial interactions in a highly controlled mode.

To verify if the addition of GelMA affected 3D microgels diameter, various formulations were generated. Figure 4 (A and B) shows the variations of particles diameter according to GelMA concentration. As optical micrographs demonstrate, particle diameters remain constant regardless of the type of formulation used, hence it becomes clear that droplet volume is the most important parameter to control 3D microgel spheres diameter upon manufacture in quasi-superhydrophobic

platforms.

Figure 4. HA-MA/GelMA 3D microgels size and morphological characterization. A) Variation of HA-MA 2.5% particles with several concentrations of GelMA. B) Variation of HA-MA 5% particles with several concentrations of GelMA. C) Representative optical micrograph of 2.5% HA-GelMA particles morphology and volume. D) Representative optical micrograph of 5% HA-GelMA particles morphology and volume. E) Top view of 2.5% HA 3D particles. F) Top view of 5% HA 3D particles. Scale bar represents 2 mm. Data is presented as mean \pm s.d., $n=12$.

The HA-MA - GelMA 3D microgels formed with 1 pL droplets presented sub-millimeter sizes similar to those generally obtained for scaffold-free *in vitro* 3D tumor spheroids. Therefore, in subsequent assays, 1 pL volumes were used to produce 3D tumor microgel models that mimic tumors microenvironment. As demonstrated, the superhydrophobic platforms allowed a significant control over 3D microgels size by manipulation of the added droplet, a major advantage when compared to other microgel producing techniques (e.g., electrospray, emulsion). In the context of 3D *in vitro* tumor models the control over microtumors size is crucial to evaluate the possible differential response of these models to anti-cancer therapeutics. Moreover, since 3D microgels size can be increased or decreased in a highly straightforward and simple mode, these platforms can be used to recapitulate small, to large, *in vivo* tumors and their ECM components. To fully characterize the supportive role of the spheroidal ECM-mimetic matrix for *in vitro* tumor models assembly

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various cell densities per microgel were investigated (Figure 5). As demonstrated 3D microgels were highly stable during culture with none of the formulations evidencing disruption of

morphological alterations (Figure 5).

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Figure 5. Optical micrographs of 3D HA-MA/GelMA PC-3 cell laden microgels along time. A and B) 2.5% and 5% HA-MA 3D microgels with 6000 PC-3 cells, respectively. C and D) 2.5% and 5% HA-MA particles with 10000 PC-3 cells, respectively. E and F) 2.5% HA-MA and 5% HA-MA particles with 20000 PC-3, respectively.

The obtained results also indicate that tumor 3D microgel models size remains unaltered along time. This is a major difference in comparison to standard scaffold-free 3D spheroids and is mainly associated to the cellular confinement in microgels.

Metabolic activity and cell death were verified by AlamarBlue (Figure 6 A to F) and Live/Dead (Figure 7) respectively. With the addition of gelatin, the metabolic activity increased over time in all 3D microgels with the various cell densities tested, a desirable result since these cultures better mimic the proliferative nature of PC-3 metastasis in bone. Moreover, this increase in cells metabolic activity was corroborated by Live/Dead analysis since no significant death was observed at 14 days. Among all the conditions, the 3D microgels with 20000 cells encapsulated were those that presented the highest metabolic activity, therefore, these conditions were chosen for the subsequent establishment of heterotypic 3D microgel PC-3:hOB tumor models. These results also indicate that the crosslinking by U.V. irradiation during 2 min (0.86 mW/cm^2) does not significantly affect cell viability. To further investigate this live/dead analysis was performed 24 h after U.V. irradiation and as the results demonstrate no significant cell death was observed (Supplementary Figure S4). This was expected in light of recent studies that investigated thoroughly the effects of U.V. irradiation in cells upon hydrogels crosslinking [51]. The internal and external structure of cell laden 3D microgels formed by digital droplet pipetting was also evaluated by scanning electron microscopy. As demonstrated in supplementary Figure S3, 3D microgels interior and exterior sections present a rough topography and cells presence both in microgels matrix and also at their surface. We hypothesize that the latter is correlated with the droplet generation process.

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Figure 6. Metabolic activity analysis of 3D microgel monocultures formed by various concentrations of gelatin and cells, at 3, 7 and 14 days. A and B) 2.5% HA-MA and 5% HA-MA particles with 6000 PC-3, respectively. C and D) 2.5% HA-MA and 5% HA-MA particles with 10000 PC-3, respectively. E and F) 2.5% HA-MA and 5% HA-MA particles with 20000 PC-3, respectively. Data is presented as mean \pm s.d., $n=5$.

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Figure 7. Widefield fluorescence micrographs of Live/Dead assays performed at 3, 7 and 14 days of PC-3 culture in HA-MA/GelMA 3D microgels. A and B) 2.5% and 5% HA-MA/GelMa 3D microgels with 6000 PC-3 cells, and varying amounts of GelMA, respectively. C and D) 2.5% and 5% HA-MA/GelMa 3D microgels with 10000 PC-3 cells, and varying amounts of GelMA, respectively. E and F) 2.5% and 5% HA-MA/GelMa 3D microgels with 20000 PC-3 cells, and varying amounts of GelMA. Green channel live cells - Calcein-AM, Red channel necrotic cells: PI.

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To demonstrate the versatility of 3D microgels in terms of cellular constituents that can be included we produced 5% GelMa - 2.5% HA-MA formulations enclosing MG-63 osteosarcoma cells. Live/dead and metabolic activity analysis demonstrate a successful cell

encapsulation of this cell type in 3D microgels and an increase in cells metabolic activity over time (Supplementary Figure S5).

Following the successful establishment of HA-MA-GelMA ECM-mimetic 3D hydrogels we also aimed to recapitulate the cellular heterogeneity found in prostate-to-bone metastasis by establishing prostate-bone cells co-cultures. The control over cancer:normal cells ratios can be easily accomplished in the 3D microgels assembled in superhydrophobic platforms. In fact, the digital droplet methodology offers a unique control for assembly of heterotypic models in comparison to other bioencapsulation techniques used for cell laden 3D microgels generation such as electrospray or microfluidics [52]. Both these techniques have been widely used for 3D microgels manufacture and cells encapsulation but require time consuming optimization, the use of solvents including sometimes oil for particles formation. The control over the number of bioencapsulated cells per particle is also highly challenging particularly in electrospray, a critical aspect when the development of 3D *in vitro* disease models for drug screening is envisioned.

3.6. HA-MA-GelMA 3D microgels for heterotypic tumor models assembly

The development of co-culture cancer:normal cells models is highly valuable for screening candidate therapeutics for prostate-to-bone metastasis treatment. Understanding the role of the bone cells that comprise this particular microenvironment (e.g., osteoblasts, osteoclasts) in cancer cells attraction, establishment and consequent interaction with the secondary tumor site, is a crucial starting point [9]. Prostate cancer metastases cause osteoblasts (excessive bone formation), osteolytic (bone lysis), or mixed bone response [10,11].

To form relevant prostate-to-bone tumor metastasis models for drug screening PC-3 cells were co-encapsulated with osteoblast cells in 3D microgels at a 1:1 ratio (Figure 8 schematics) [10]. This ratio was selected from previous literature reports that indicate it to be a suitable representation of prostate-to-bone *in vitro* models [10]. Figure 8 A and B displays optical images of the established 3D heterotypic microgel models containing the tumor ECM-mimicking components (HA-MA and GelMA). The developed models in superhydrophobic platforms also display a homogeneous cellular distribution in 3D microgels volume and all the structures remained stable up to 14 days. Also, no noticeable change in 3D microgels size was observed during cell culture (Figure 8).

631 Figure 8. Establishment of 3D microgel heterotypic PC-3:hOB co-culture models. Schematics of
632 prostate-to-bone 3D microgel tumor models. Optical images of 3D tumor models of HA-MA-
GelMA
633 with PC-3 and hOB. Optical contrast micrographs of: A) Co-culture of HA-MA 2.5% and GelMA
634 with 1:1 ratio of PC-3 and hOB and B) Co-culture of HA-MA 5% and GelMA with 1: 1 ratio of PC-
635 3 and hOB. C and D) Widefield fluorescence micrographs of PC-3:hOB 3D co-culture HA-MA-
636 GelMA microgels Live/Dead analysis at 3, 7 and 14 days of culture. Green channel live cells -
637 Calcein-AM, Red channel necrotic cells: PI. E and F) Metabolic activity of 3D heterotypic PC-
3:hOB
638 microgel models. E) Co-culture of HA-MA 2.5% and GelMA at PC-3:hOB 1:1 ratio. F) Co-culture
639 of HA-MA 5% at PC-3:hOB 1:1 ratio. Data is presented as mean \pm s.d., $n=5$.

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640 Live/Dead analysis (Figure 8 C) disclosed minimal cell death at later culture stages in
641 2.5%-HA-MA-GelMA 5% formulation, at 14 days, indicating ECM-mimetic 3D microgels
642 suitability as cell supportive 3D scaffolds. Metabolic assays (Figure 8 E and F) demonstrate
643 an increase in cells metabolic activity over time. This is a positive aspect of the established
644 models, since osteoblasts are associated with the proliferation of prostate cancer cells *in vivo*.
645 The metabolic activity at 14 days in the HA-MA 2.5%-GelMA 5% and HA-MA 5%-GelMA
646 5% conditions is slightly higher than on the other conditions tested and for this reason these
647 conditions were selected for testing of drug. Following this, the evaluation of bone specific
648 markers in the established 3D ECM-cell rich microtumor tissues was investigated.

649 **3.7. 3D microgel heterotypic *in vitro* tumor models mineralization**

650 Matrix mineralization consists of the deposit of bone tissue components, including
651 extracellular calcium deposits. The presence of calcium in 3D PC-3:hOB co-culture
652 microgels was determined by using the Alizarin Red S assay which provides a red coloration
653 if calcium deposits are detected (Figure 9). The obtained results clearly demonstrate that
654 along time calcium deposits are more evident. Interestingly, a higher calcium deposition was
655 obtained for 3D microgels assembled with higher gelatin concentration (Figure 9 A6 and
656 B6). These important results demonstrate the effect of osteoblasts when in close culture with
657 PC-3, as previously discussed and evidence the bioactivity of bone forming cells upon
658 bioencapsulation in the fabricated 3D ECM-mimetic microgels.

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Figure 10. Widefield fluorescence micrographs of cell-specific tracking in different 3D microgels at 7 and 14 days. PC-3 were stained with DiO (blue), and hOB with DiD (red). Scale bars represent 200 μm.

understand the organization and behavior of co-cultured prostate-bone

microgel matrix, we labeled PC-3 with DiO and hOB with DiD cell

tracking fluorophores. Following successful labelling, the 3D distribution and aggregation

patterns of the different co-culture populations were evaluated at 7 and 14 days (Figure 10).

Interestingly the fluorescence signaling of PC-3 (blue) was always higher than that of hOB

cells.

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Such results could be attributed to the higher cell proliferation rate of PC-3 cells when compared to that of human osteoblasts and is an important factor that must be taken into consideration by researchers performing drug screening assays in complex co-culture models. Moreover, cell-specific tracking assays demonstrate that no preferential spatial organization of PC-3 or hOB occurs during confinement in 3D microgels matrix. Taking this data into consideration the formed 3D microgels were then used for the evaluation of cisplatin cytotoxic potential.

3.9. Anti-cancer drug screening in 3D microgel *in vitro* tumor models

The formulations of 2.5% HA-MA- GelMA 5% and 5% HA-MA - GelMA 5% in which a higher calcium deposit was observed were selected for drug screening assays. Before performing the drug screening assays, scaffold-free monotypic and heterotypic 3D tumor spheroids were established via forced floating techniques (Supplementary Figure S3) and were used as controls to evaluate the influence of tumor ECM mimetic 3D microgels. The size, morphology and shape of control 3D spheroids was monitored over 5, 7 and 14 days. It is clearly observable that monotypic and heterotypic 3D spheroids have different sizes and morphologies (Supplementary Figure S6). The microtumors size in both cultures increases over time; however, the spheroids containing hOB are significantly more compact, a feature that is not visible in monotypic 3D spheroids. This clearly demonstrates the effect of PC-3 and hOB cell-cell interactions, evidencing its importance in the recapitulation of prostate- bone metastasis *in vitro*.

For anti-cancer drug screening studies 3D microgel co-cultures were subjected to various concentrations of cisplatin (100 pM, to 250 pM) an anti-cancer pharmaceutical clinically approved for the treatment of bone cancer [40]. As demonstrated in Figure 11 A an increase in cisplatin administered dose to all tested models (3D microgels, 3D spheroids) leads to decreased cell viability. The cell viability was accessed via ATP quantification since no observable change in 3D microgels volume, that could be correlated to cell death, was observed. A reduction in tumor volume is mainly observable in standard scaffold-free 3D spheroid model where only cells comprise the microtumor, but these lack important ECM mimetic components.

The evaluation of cisplatin cytotoxicity in heterotypic co-cultures showed that HA-MA 2.5%-GelMA 5% 3D microgels have slightly higher drug resistance than HA-MA 5% -

GelMA 5%. The observed differences could be correlated with higher cellular bioactivity in HA-MA 2.5%-GelMA 5% 3D microgels. In fact, as previously demonstrated, at day 7 and 14, 3D microgels of HA-MA 2.5%-GelMA 5% present higher calcium deposition. Interestingly, 3D microgels present slightly higher resistance to cisplatin activity when compared to their 3D spheroid counterparts. This supports the importance of including ECM mimetic supports in 3D *in vitro* tumor models as they provide more *in vivo* like cues to cultured cells.

The obtained results indicate that HA-MA 2.5% /GelMA 5% 3D spherical microgels have potential to be used for

Figure 11. Cisplatin cytotoxicity evaluation. A) Normalized dose dependent heat map of cell viability following administration of various cisplatin concentrations. Data is represented as mean, $n=3$. B) 3D cell viability analysis of 3D *in vitro* tumor models incubated with the highest cisplatin concentration (250 pM). Data is presented as mean \pm s.e.m., $n=3$.

screening of candidate anti-cancer therapeutics that target prostate- to-bone metastatic niches. Moreover, these findings evidence the importance of evaluating different ECM-like hydrogel formulations during drug screening so a final decision over a particular treatment performance can be inferred.

The 3D microtumors producing methodology described herein is highly versatile in various aspects since it can be adapted: (i) for using different ECM-mimicking biomaterials (Matrigel®, collagen), (ii) for generating different size 3D microgels by simply changing the droplet volume and (iii) for using different types of cells (immune system cells, patient derived tumor cells), and cell-cell co-cultures (e.g., dual, tri-cultures, etc). This versatility allied with the cost-effectiveness of the produced surfaces increase its applicability potential.

When compared to other methodologies such as scaffold-free forced floating technologies or centrifugal-based seeding for 3D tumor models generation, the use of SH-surface generated 3D microgels have the advantage of including ECM-mimetic scaffolds (GelMa/HA-MA) where cells can attach and proliferate, therefore providing a closer recapitulation of the tumor-ECM components found *in vivo* tumors. The inclusion of tumor ECM components in 3D *in vitro* tumor models is paramount for obtaining microtumors with close to *in vivo* features.

Moreover, in comparison to other cell bioencapsulation methodologies digital droplet generation of 3D microgel tumor models in superhydrophobic (SH) surfaces is performed in-air, in a solvent-free approach that overcomes the issues of cell-enclosing microcapsule technologies such as those developed by Sakay and co-workers which involve the use of liquid paraffin microgels generation[53]. Liquid paraffin may affect cells bioactivity and its removal is labor intensive generally involving several washing-centrifugation steps and its full elimination is very difficult to be quantified. The proposed droplet/SH surfaces also overcome the solvent-based issues of microfluidic platforms for spheroid 3D microgels generation which require the use of mineral oil-based phases and surfactants for microdroplet generation[54,55].

4. Conclusions

Herein we have engineered a superhydrophobic surface to rapidly produce spheroidal 3D disease model of prostate cancer in mono and co-culture in-air, on solvent free conditions. The *in vitro* generated microtumors exhibited tumor-associated characteristics, such as calcium matrix deposit. This result emphasizes the interaction between PC-3 and osteoblasts to promote the bioactivity of bone-forming cells. The evaluation of cisplatin cytotoxicity in heterotypic co-cultures showed that 2.5% HA-MA-GelMA 5% microgels have slightly higher drug resistance. It is important to highlight that the ease of manufacture of these platforms and of photocrosslinkable 3D spherical microgels allows a rapid and large scale generation of tumor-tailored *in vitro* spheroidal models.

We envisage that the current 3D microgel prostate-to-bone tumor model may be improved in the future with the addition of other cell types including osteoclasts since they play a major role in prostate metastasis in bone. 3D microgels can also be used in the future to perform more fundamental analysis such as those pertaining to drug penetration/distribution in tumor models volume. The robust and reproducible generation of cell rich tumor-ECM mimetic microgels in the superhydrophobic polystyrene surface allows their cost-effective translation to 96- or 384-well plates or other culture platforms that are suitable for high throughput/high content screening. Such will unlock the possibility to accelerate the discovery of new/repurposed therapeutics or therapeutics combinations for this type of metastasis.

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